

The Use of Metasurfaces to Enhance Microwave Imaging: Experimental Validation for Tomographic and Radar-Based Algorithms

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ABSTRACT Over the last two decades, metamaterials (MMs) and metasurfaces (MTSs) have been used to fabricate innovative antenna designs, offering cost-effective solutions compared to conventional radiating systems. This paper investigates the feasibility of combining MM design concepts and imaging techniques to create innovative microwave imaging systems. In particular, we present an experimental study with the aim of enhancing microwave imaging for haemorrhagic stroke detection using a new MTS design. First, we show the improvement in performance for a stand-alone MTS-loaded antenna, by studying its operating characteristics in the near and far fields. Then, we assess the performance of the MTS on the reconstruction results from simulations and measurements on two tissue-mimicking gel-based brain phantoms with a cylindrical target representing the bleeding in haemorrhagic stroke. The brain phantom was immersed inside an imaging tank filled with 90% glycerol matching liquid. To perform the image reconstructions, we used both a Huygens based radar algorithm and a DBIM-TwIST tomography algorithm. Our simulation and measurement results indicate that the proposed MTS design improves target localization and decreases image artefacts for the tomographic algorithm and enables target's detection through our radar technique, paving the way for a hybrid microwave imaging prototype with MTS enhanced antennas.

INDEX TERMS Brain imaging, metasurfaces (MTSs), microwave imaging (MWI), microwave tomography, radar imaging.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, we can take advantage of metamaterials' (MMs') ability of manipulating size, efficiency, bandwidth and directivity of different systems to fabricate innovative structures for radiating and scattering applications. A MM is a synthetic composite material that exhibits exotic properties, not usually found in natural materials, such as negative refractive index (NRI). Metasurfaces (MTSs) are the two-dimensional counterparts of MMs. These artificial sheet materials are mainly based on thin layers made of sub-wavelength resonators. The high flexibility design process

of MTSs has led to numerous innovative antenna designs, revolutionizing a variety of existing techniques in different fields.

Electrically small MM-based resonant radiating systems can be employed to overcome limits usually associated with electromagnetic (EM) problems [1]. For example, resonances arising from double negative materials (media with negative constitutive parameters ϵ and μ) provide a means to engineer the systems' performance [2]. Also, despite their non-resonant character, zero-index metamaterials (materials with permittivity and permeability of zero or near-zero

values) have strong impact in some applications and can be used to achieve high directivity antennas [3]. At microwave frequencies, MTS antennas can be designed so that the MTS interacts with the emitted wave to form a desired radiation pattern or guide a surface wave [4].

Recently, several split-ring resonators (SRRs) structures have been designed for different applications, including microwave (MW) sensing and imaging [5]. For instance, SRR-based MTS have been used for developing MW biosensors [6], [7]. Also, MM lenses have been used in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), to manipulate the field detected by the coils [8], and in [9] to generate various illuminating incident fields for microwave imaging (MWI). In the K-band frequencies, frequency-diverse MTS apertures are used for security-screening applications [10], [11]. Our SRR-based MM film has been proposed in [12] as a coating for MW brain imaging, able to reduce reflection and improve the transmitted power into a body region such as the head. More recent work on the use of MTSs for MWI include studies on absorbing [13] and high-impedance [14] MTSs. Impedance mismatch is a phenomenon occurring when EM waves propagate between media with different dielectric properties, resulting in a reduction in the transmitted energy. This mismatch is significant in sensing and biomedical imaging, due to the high value of the relative permittivity and conductivity of tissues compared to air. Thus, it is important to maximize the transmitted power through biological tissues to detect the target under investigation [15]. This issue is particularly relevant in MWI for biomedical applications.

In the last decades, microwave medical imaging has attracted growing interest, motivated by the existence of differences in the dielectric properties between the tissues. The research in this field was originally focused on breast cancer detection, while recent research efforts have been extended to other applications such as brain stroke detection. Several imaging modalities are currently used to assist the medical professionals in diagnosing strokes, most notably MRI and computed tomography (CT). However, these technologies are not fast or portable (due to their dimensions), nor can they be used at rural medical centers or be carried by first response service which is essential for saving a person experiencing a stroke. In addition, MRI systems are very expensive and time-consuming [16].

In comparison with these technologies, MWI is capable of providing a portable detection system, and thus present the initial diagnosis of various emergency life-threatening circumstances such as strokes due to brain injury. For example, the possibility of detecting the type of stroke accurately inside an ambulance can save critical therapy time [17]. MWI brain imaging systems are separated into tomographic and radar-based techniques. The former solves a non-linear, electromagnetic inverse problem through approximating the dielectric contrast between the unknown and known tissues' properties [18]. Radar-based techniques solve a less complex problem of discovering a scattering map contingent on the contrast present between the dielectric properties of brain tissues.

This paper presents reconstruction results performed on two different realizations of a tissue-mimicking gel-based brain phantom with a cylindrical target (permittivity of 60 at 1 GHz) representing the bleeding during a haemorrhagic stroke. For this purpose, the cylindrical target was positioned at two distinct locations within the phantom to verify its detection and localization. Compact antennas operating between 0.5-2 GHz immersed into a matching medium have been employed to tackle the strong attenuation of the EM waves inside the human head [19]. Inspired by our previous work [12], the antennas are loaded with MTS structures to enhance the signals scattered from the target.

To test the impact of the MTS enhancement on the MWI system, we employ both a tomographic as well as a radar-based approach. Implementations are based on the distorted Born iterative method (DBIM) combined with a two-step iterative shrinkage/thresholding method (TwIST) [20], [21], and a Huygens-based radar method [22], respectively. The presented simulation and measurement results show that an accurate detection and localization can be achieved using both types of algorithm. To the best of our knowledge this is the first paper presenting a comparative investigation of MWI for stroke detection combining MTS coated antennas and both tomography and radar-based algorithms. A preliminary investigation of testing both our tomographic and radar-based algorithms on phantom-based measurements, inspiring this work has recently been published by the authors in [23]. Furthermore, we also note that our tomographic approach has been experimentally validated in [24]. This work however provides further investigation by presenting CST results and verifying target detection and localization on two phantoms with different target locations.

The rest of this manuscript is structured as follows. The MTS design and its performance results are described in Section II. Section III provides the methodology and description of the DBIM-TwIST and Huygens methods. Section IV details the measurement setup, the phantom preparation and fabrication procedure, while all the related simulation and measurement results are presented and discussed in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines the planned future research.

II. METASURFACE DESIGN

A. UNIT CELL METASURFACE DESIGN

Our MTS design is based on simulation studies carried out using models of lossy biological tissues. In particular, our simulation results serve as an estimate of the improvement in transmission when impedance matching is achieved by placing a MTS in front of skin tissue. Here, we extend the investigation of the MTS introduced in [12], [25] through description of its design procedure and its performance analysis in terms of transmission and reflection parameters, gain and radiation efficiency.

A first MTS unit cell was designed to act as an impedance matching in the presence of a simplified planar model of the head. The design of the unit cell was initially based on

a plane wave analysis inspired by [26], [27]. This analysis is tailored to the desired operation bandwidth (selected as 0.5-2.0 GHz for our head imaging application) and is based on a slab model of tissue layers interacting with the MTS [12]. We then created a finite MTS structure from the unit cell by fitting the antenna's surface with a suitable number of unit cells. Keeping the unit cell design and size fixed, a 2D surface that best fits the antenna was generated. Aside from fitting the MTS to the antenna dimensions, our design process does not require any further adjustment to the specific antenna design. The MTS unit cell comprises a Jerusalem Cross metallic lattice (thickness = 0.10 mm) embedded between two Rogers 3010 TM substrates (thickness = 1.27 mm, $\epsilon' = 10.2$ and $\tan \delta = 0.0022$). The two Rogers high-dielectric substrates are bonded with Rogers 3001 bonding film ($\epsilon' = 2.28$, $\tan \delta = 0.003$).

As described in [25], the head model comprises seven flat tissue layers placed in the following order: skin, cortical bone (outer layer), cancellous bone, cortical bone (inner layer), cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), gray matter and white matter. The dielectric properties of the tissues at 1 GHz were taken from [28]. The interaction of this setup with a linearly polarized plane wave in the 0.5–2 GHz frequency range was modeled in CST Microwave Studio. The S-parameters were calculated considering “Port 1” before the lossy dielectric medium (thickness $t = 5$ mm, permittivity $\epsilon' = 18$ and conductivity $\sigma = 1.3$ S/m at 1 GHz) and “Port 2” after the white matter layer.

The improvement in transmission obtained with different geometries was studied. The design was optimized manually until the performance achieved was close to the expected. In particular, variations in the classic Jerusalem Cross design were introduced in order to reduce the reflection coefficient. After that, CST optimizer tool with a Trust Region Framework algorithm was used to tune the MTS, setting maximum transmission across all the frequency range as a goal. The introduction of additional metal wires in the simple Jerusalem Cross structure (see MTS2) reduced reflection and increased transmission (by about 1.5 dB) in the whole frequency range.

The change in the reflection parameter due to the additional metallisation can be easily understood by modeling the metal sections using a lumped LC network analogy [29]. Each resonator is linked to a different equivalent circuit model. The metal wires in the last design represent additional inductances and introduce new gap capacitances in the Jerusalem Cross equivalent circuit (Fig. 3), producing new inductive and capacitive effects.

B. IMPACT OF MTS ON ANTENNA PERFORMANCE

Our MTS-enhanced antenna consists of the triangular antenna described in Section IV, plus a MTS superstrate loading (24.75 mm × 29.7 mm), based on the unit cell illustrated in Fig. 1 (MTS final design, i.e., MTS2).

Before investigating the 8-port system, the interaction between two antennas in the near-field was studied in CST

FIGURE 1. MTS1 design (left), MTS2 design (center), side-view (right).

FIGURE 2. (a) Reflection parameter comparison between MTS1 and MTS2, (b) transmission comparison between MTS designs and in the absence of MTS.

FIGURE 3. Jerusalem Cross equivalent circuit.

Microwave Studio. Reflection and transmission parameters were calculated (with and without MTS) for two different setups. The first setup includes two antennas placed at a distance of 127 mm and immersed in a tank filled with 90% glycerol. The second setup includes the lossy matching medium and our elliptical head phantom. This head model includes an external plastic layer ($\epsilon = 2.56$; $\tan \delta = 0.0119$) and average brain tissue inside ($\epsilon = 45.8$; $\sigma = 0.76$ S/m). The antennas were closely fixed on the elliptical head phantom, along its smallest dimension, at a distance of 127 mm.

Fig. 4 shows that the transmission coefficient S_{21} is considerably higher in the presence of the MTS in both cases, while the antenna's reflection coefficient S_{11} is not enhanced by the MTS. We note that the transmission enhancement in Fig. 4 is much higher than the 1.5-2.0 dB observed in Fig. 2. This may be due to the fact that a finite MTS structure is used (rather than a unit cell as in Fig. 2), and that a much simpler phantom (with fewer reflection layers and much lower total loss) is used in our experiments. Specifically, the presence of the MTS can enhance the antenna's radiation efficiency and hence lead to much higher transmission enhancement than in the simulations of a plane wave incident on a unit cell, which are used to calculate transmission

FIGURE 4. (a) Reflection, and (b) transmission parameters comparison with and without the MTS final design (MTS2).

FIGURE 5. Reflection and transmission parameters of the MTS on the head model and adjacent to the antenna.

in Fig. 2. The MTS' impedance-matching property refers to this transmission enhancement, rather than to improving the impedance match of the antenna itself. However, improving the antenna's impedance match is also possible, as we have shown in our previous work with spear patch antennas [24], where improvements in both transmission and reflection measured coefficients were observed when using the MTS.

The impact of the distance of the MTS from the radiating element was also studied. To this end, two antennas were placed at a distance of 137 mm along the smallest dimension of the elliptical head phantom and the MTS superstrate loading was placed at two different positions: on the head model's surface and adjacent to the antenna's substrate. The S21-parameters shown in Fig. 5 indicate that the improvement in transmission is overall more significant when the MTS is placed adjacent to the radiating elements.

As a further analysis of the MTS's impact on the antenna's performance, gain and radiation efficiency were calculated with and without MTS superstrate loading. These antenna characteristics (with and without MTS) are shown in Fig. 6. To isolate the MTS effect, we also simulated a new "negative control (NC)" scenario where the substrate without the MTS-defining metallic elements is placed on the antennas. The antenna was immersed in a $100 \times 100 \times 100$ mm block of 90% coupling medium and an antenna far-field characterization was run in CST Microwave Studio. The graphs show that, within the physical limitations due to the lossy matching medium [30], [31], the MTS superstrate loading enhances the antenna's far-field characteristics.

In addition to increasing the antenna's gain and radiation efficiency as shown in Fig. 6, the MTS enhances the

FIGURE 6. (a) Antenna's gain with MTS (blue solid lines), without MTS (blue dashed lines) and with NC loading (green solid lines). (b) Antenna's radiation efficiency with MTS (blue solid lines), without MTS (blue dashed lines) and with NC loading (green solid lines).

FIGURE 7. Normalized E-field plots for an antenna transmitting in our simulated experimental setup without MTS (left), with MTS (center), and loaded only with a substrate used as "negative control (NC)" (right).

antenna's responsiveness to the target's response. This has been demonstrated in our previous work by comparing the (weak) signal scattered from the target and received by antennas with and without the MTS at various positions in the imaging domain (e.g., [12, Fig. 12]). To showcase this effect, we simulated one of our experiments in CST and plotted the calculated normalized electric field distributions at a representative frequency of 1.25 GHz in Fig. 7. Comparing the field distributions in these plots show a stronger signal in the target area when the MTS is used, which translates into a stronger target response and hence higher data quality for the imaging system. This improvement, however, is also observed for the negative control case of substrate-only loaded antenna. In the absence of the MTS, however, the resulting reconstructions for the substrate-only loaded antenna fail to detect the target, as illustrated in Section V.

To demonstrate the MTS's impact on the radiated field, we calculated the E-field at two points belonging to different imaging planes and located in the centre of the head. For all the array configurations, the E-field intensity values in those points were computed for a model of the head made of average brain only ("no target" scenario) and for the same model including a blood-mimicking target ("with target" scenario). Then, the difference between the E-field intensity values calculated in the two scenarios (ΔE) was estimated. Values of the scattered fields for the "No MTS", "MTS", "NC" configurations are shown in Table 1. Our results suggest that the field scattered from the target inclusion has a higher intensity when the MTS is present.

TABLE 1. Differences between E-field intensity values at 2 different points for “No MTS”, “MTS” and “NC” configurations.

	Point1 (0,60,0) mm	Point2 (0,43,0) mm
ΔE (no MTS)	0.41 V/m	0.65 V/m
ΔE (MTS)	0.50 V/m	0.81 V/m
ΔE (NC)	0.47 V/m	0.76 V/m

FIGURE 8. E-field distribution on the surface of the head phantom for the “No MTS”, “MTS”, “NC” scenarios when antenna 1 (T1) is transmitting. The MTS produces a wider E-field distribution.

FIGURE 9. E-field plotted on the transmitter’s substrate for the “No MTS”, “MTS”, “NC” scenarios with the head model. A higher-intensity E-field is transmitted when the MTS is present.

Fig. 8 shows the total E-field distribution normalized to 35 dB on the surface of the head phantom at 1.25 GHz for antenna 1 (T1) transmitting with and without MTS. In this figure, the E-field distribution for the NC case-study is also included. The plots show that the MTS does not focus the E-field onto a tighter beam, but on the contrary, it widens the E-field distribution inside the head model, resulting in better signal coverage. We postulate that this is the reason that the target response is stronger in the presence of the MTS, leading to better target detection.

Moreover, the E-field distributions on the transmitting antennas (patch and MTS/NC surfaces) for the “No MTS”, “MTS”, “NC” scenarios (with and without the head model) shown in Fig. 9 indicate that a stronger field is excited by the transmitter’s substrate when the MTS is present.

However, it is important to notice that this higher-field intensity on the antenna’s substrate covered by the MTS sheet may be due to the fact that the monopole’s radiating part is not in direct contact with our lossy coupling medium. Thus, to validate the MTS’s impact on the antenna array, we have also carried out CST simulations to study the MTS’s behavior in receiving mode. Our results suggest that the MTS seems to act as an “amplifier” of the received field. To show this enhancement, we considered different antenna arrays (“No MTS”, “MTS”, “NC”) immersed in matching medium only. The first array includes a triangular patch transmitter (antenna 1) and 7 MTS-enhanced receivers. The second array consists of the same transmitter and 7 negative-control receivers. The E-field was plotted on the substrate of the receiver opposite to the transmitter (with and without MTS and with NC). Fig. 10 shows that the E-field on

FIGURE 10. E-field plotted on the substrate of receiver 5 (with and without MTS and with NC loading) when antenna 1 is transmitting. A higher-intensity E-field is received when the MTS is present.

receiver 5 is significantly enhanced when the MTS covers the antenna’s substrate. Thus, considering the same source of excitation, the MTS leads to an improvement of the received field.

III. IMAGING METHODOLOGY

A. DBIM-TWIST ALGORITHM

In DBIM method, a non-linear EM inverse scattering problem is solved through approximating the overall electrical field under the Born approximation:

$$E_s(r_n, r_m) = E(r_n, r_m) - E_b(r_n, r_m) \\ = \omega^2 \mu \int_V G_b(r_n, r) E_b(r, r_m) (\epsilon(r) - \epsilon_b(r)) dr \quad (1)$$

where E , E_b and E_s indicate the total, background, and scattered fields, and r_m , r_n represent receiver and transmitter positions, respectively. The function $(\epsilon(r) - \epsilon_b(r))$ denotes the contrast between the complex permittivity of the known background and the unknown region [32]. The achieved linear problem is still ill-posed, and hence the TwIST method [33] is employed. The dielectric contrast function is estimated during each DBIM iteration, and added to the background profile that is subsequently used for calculating the new background electrical field. Next, we apply the first-order Debye model to capture the dispersive behavior of the materials:

$$\epsilon_s(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{1 + j\omega\tau} + j\frac{\sigma_s}{\omega\epsilon_0} \quad (2)$$

where the parameters ϵ_∞ , $\Delta\epsilon$ and σ_s are updated at each iteration. Lastly, we reconstruct the Debye parameters and use them to determine the complex permittivity within the reconstruction domain [20], [32].

B. HUYGENS PRINCIPLE-BASED ALGORITHM

The radar-based Huygens algorithm, initially presented in [34], has shown its potential for use in medical applications [35]. Consider a human head which is illuminated by a transmitter TX_m , operating at a frequency range f_i . We have R receivers, with receiver r at location ρ_r measuring the field $E_{rm}(f_i)$ from transmitter m at frequency f_i . The Huygens algorithm measures the field on the external surface of the medium $E_{rm}(f_i)$ and back-propagates it virtually inside the imaging domain. In this way, the internal field

FIGURE 11. Measurement hardware and setup for radar (left), and tomography (right).

within the medium is reconstructed as:

$$E_{\text{HP}}(\rho, m, f_i) = \sum_{r=1}^R E_{rm}(f_i) G(k|\rho_r - \rho|) \quad (3)$$

where $G(k_1|\rho_r - \rho|) = \frac{1}{4\pi} e^{-jk_1|\rho_r - \rho|}$ as defined in [34] at locations ρ , while k represents the complex wave number of the background medium (90% glycerol here). It should be pointed out that, similar to our previous publications, we have opted to use a 3D, free-space resembling Green's function in (3), instead of 0-th order Hankel function for 2D radar reconstructions. This has been done to preserve a better generalization of the algorithm and a uniform formulation for our future extension to 3D imaging scenarios [36].

To remove the common artefacts appearing in the reconstructed images, subtraction of the signals from the phantom with and without target has been used to remove the artefact image. Thus, (3) is modified as follows:

$$E'_{\text{HP}}(\rho, m, f_i) = \sum_{r=1}^R (E_{rm} - E_{rm(\text{noTarget})}) G(k_1|\rho_r - \rho|) \quad (4)$$

As a final step, to calculate the total intensity we incoherently sum all the transmitting positions and all the recorded frequencies.

$$I_{\text{HP}}(\rho) = \sum_{m=1}^M \left[\sum_{l=1}^L E'_{\text{HP}}(\rho, m, f_l) \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

All measurements presented in this research were carried out using a custom-made MWI setup [37], which is compatible for both radar and tomographic configurations. The setup comprises of a 300 mm diameter cylindrical tank, shielded by an RF absorbing sheet from Laird Technologies EMI. The transmitting and receiving antennas are positioned in a circular ring inside the acrylic tank (Fig. 11). Vertical and horizontal mounts are used to adjust the precision and accuracy of antenna positions. Transmitter and receiver are connected to a multiport vector network analyser (Keysight M9019A).

In this work, inverted triangular patch antennas [38], designed on a 24 mm by 30 mm FR-4 substrate were used.

FIGURE 12. Triangular antenna without (left) and with MTS coating (right).

TABLE 2. Quantities of materials used for 100 ml of tissue mimicking phantoms.

	Average brain	Blood
Gelatin powder	11 gr	16 gr
Kerosene	13 ml	-
Propanol	2.5 ml	1.5 ml
Safflower oil	13 ml	-
Surfactant	4 ml	-
Water	60 ml	80 ml

Triangular antenna's photos both with and without MTS coating are depicted in Fig. 12.

Different antenna configurations for tomographic and radar-based measurements were used. For tomography measurements, an elliptically configured 8-antenna array was immersed inside the tank, and the antennas were positioned as close as possible to the phantom's external surface without touching it. The 8 antennas performed both as receivers and transmitters, creating an 8×8 scattering matrix which was fed into DBIM-TwIST. Meanwhile, only 2 antennas were used for the radar measurements, one performing as the transmitter and the other as receiver. For each radar-based measurement, the transmitting antenna was positioned 30 mm away from the elliptical brain phantom at its larger axis of 170 mm, while the receiving antenna was placed closer at only 10 mm away from the largest axis of the brain phantom. For each transmitter position, the receiving antenna was rotated radially (anti-clockwise) with 15° steps, measuring the external field of the phantom at 24 receiving positions. Both types of measurements recorded a frequency band of 0.5 to 2 GHz. In all cases, antennas were immersed in 90% glycerol solution inside water with permittivity of ≈ 17 at 1 GHz, which was used as the matching medium.

To examine the performance of both algorithms experimentally, gelatin-oil mixtures based on the phantom preparation method described in [39], and investigated on phantoms in [21], [23], were prepared. Two mixtures were produced to mimic the average brain and blood layers. The recipe and concentration of each material used in preparing the mixtures is presented in Table 2.

The preparation process started with preparing a water-gelatine mixture, which was mixed until the gelatine particles were fully dissolved resulting in a transparent mixture. Next, propanol was added to remove the air bubbles from the surface. When the mixture reached 70°C , a 50% kerosene-safflower oil solution was added to the existing mixture and stirred at the same temperature, until the oil particles were

FIGURE 13. Elliptical brain phantom before (left) and after (right) inserting the eccentric target. The target was positioned at two different locations in the two constructed phantoms.

fully dissolved. The mixture was stirred until the temperature dropped to 50°C, at which point surfactant was added. As a final step, at 35°C the prepared mixture was poured inside a thin elliptical plastic mould (Fig. 13), and was left to cool and solidify until measurements were performed the next day. The 3D printed ABS mould with a length of 170 mm and width of 120 mm was used both as a holder for the brain mimicking liquid mixture and to act as an additional phantom layer during image reconstruction.

Before inserting the target into the average brain mixture, we first measured the “no target” scenario using both tomography and radar antenna configurations, with both “without MTS” and “with MTS” antenna types. After performing all the “no target” measurements, we proceeded to “with target” measurements by placing a 30 mm diameter cylindrical shaped target mimicking the blood inside the average brain solution. This was done through creating a hole in the phantom, and extracting a part of the brain mixture using a cylindrical mould, resulting in the creation of a cylindrical cavity with a diameter of 30 mm. Next, the cavity was filled with the blood target mixture (Fig. 13). The target was placed at a distance of 30 mm horizontally to the right and 25 mm vertically downwards from the center of the phantom [30, -25], at an angular position of ≈ 320 degrees relative to the position of the first transmitting antenna. The target was prepared with a similar recipe to that of the brain, but without the use of safflower oil and kerosene (Table 2), providing a mixture with permittivity of ≈ 65 and conductivity of ≈ 0.4 S/m at 1 GHz, mimicking the dielectric properties of blood during haemorrhage stroke. Next, all the “with target” measurements for both tomography and radar configurations, both with and without MTS were performed.

In order to verify that the target detection for the first phantom corresponded to the haemorrhage blood target region and not to an anomaly or an artefact, we prepared a second phantom one week after the first set of measurements. The target for the second phantom was positioned eccentrically, placed 30 mm horizontally to the left and 25 mm vertically downwards from the phantom’s center with respect to the first antenna position [-30, -25].

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All images presented in this section have been obtained by subtracting the signals from the phantom before and after inserting the target. The final MTS design (MTS2) was used

FIGURE 14. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 1 at three different frequencies using data from the CST model and antennas without (left) and with the MTS (right).

in all simulations and measurements presented here. Before proceeding with the measurements, the experimental setup was simulated in CST Microwave Studio software to check the functionality and performance of the MTS and the algorithms in the given configuration. The simulations were done using an 8-antenna array configuration and the same configuration was used for both DBIM-TwIST and Huygens algorithms.

Fig. 14 shows the DBIM-TwIST results for 3 different frequencies corresponding to Phantom 1 without and with MTS. An improvement in the target localization, with less artefacts can be obtained when using MTS. Similarly, simulation results of Phantom 2 are depicted in Fig. 15, before and after applying the MTS. It should be pointed out that for both no MTS and with MTS cases, the same incident field model of ideal point sources has been used in the FDTD forward solver used by the DBIM algorithm. This is common practice in inverse scattering algorithms, where modeling fully patch antennas is computationally impossible. Our calibration method accounts to some extent for this mismatch between these simple antenna models and the true antennas used by our system. Moreover, it should be noted that all the reconstructed tomography images presented here represent the real part of the complex permittivity (dielectric constant) of the tissues. As we have shown in our previous work [21], the imaginary part and hence conductivity of the tissues can also be estimated but with less accuracy.

FIGURE 15. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 2 at three different frequencies using data from the CST model and antennas without (left) and with the MTS (right).

FIGURE 16. Radar-based images after normalization and adjustment for: (a) Phantom 1, and (b) Phantom 2, using data from the CST model and antennas with the MTS. Axes units are meters.

Moving on to the radar simulation results, Figs. 16(a) and (b) show the normalized and adjusted reconstructed intensity images corresponding to Phantoms 1 and 2 with the MTS, respectively. The image adjustment procedure allows us to have a better and clearer visualization of the target and the region of interest, and is done here by converting intensity values lower than 0.65 to 0, and re-ranging values higher than 0.65, from 0 to 1. In both cases, the target can be localized in its approximate position without artefacts. In comparison, no detection is achieved without the use of MTS on the antennas as depicted in Figs. 17(a) and (b).

To demonstrate the positive impact of the MTS on radar-based detection, we have also considered the case of Phantom 1 with simulated data and the negative control scenario defined in Section II, where the antenna is loaded

FIGURE 17. Radar-based images after normalization and adjustment for: (a) Phantom 1, and (b) Phantom 2, using data from the CST model and antennas without the MTS. Axes units are meters.

FIGURE 18. Radar-based image after normalization and adjustment for Phantom 1, using data from the CST model and the negative control scenario defined in Section II, where the antenna is loaded with a substrate only. Axes units are meters.

FIGURE 19. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 1 at different frequencies using experimental data and antennas without the MTS.

with a substrate only. Although the electric field distribution plotted in Fig. 7 for this case is very similar to the case of the MTS, the resulting reconstruction in Fig. 18 shows a stronger ghost target close to the real one, which obstructs accurate detection. This example suggests that using the MTS can

FIGURE 20. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 1 at different frequencies using experimental data and antennas with the MTS.

FIGURE 21. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 2 at different frequencies using experimental data and antennas without the MTS.

enhance detection by virtue of its transmitting and receiving properties, which increases the target response relative to other signal artifacts.

Focusing now on the reconstruction results from the measurements, Figs. 19 and 20 show the reconstructed images using DBIM-TwIST for 6 different frequencies in the range of 1-1.5 GHz for Phantom 1 without and with MTS, respectively. These results show a more clear improvement in target detection when using the MTS than the improvement observed with the simulated data. Similar improvement can be noticed for images corresponding to Phantom 2, depicted in Figs. 21 and 22 before and after applying the MTS, respectively. To quantify these improvements, Fig. 23 shows the reconstruction error metrics for both tomography simulations and measurements, at 1.2 GHz.

Referring to radar measurements, Fig. 24 shows the S-parameter comparison for the recorded frequency band (0.5-2 GHz) of Phantom 1 without and with MTS, when the triangular antennas are closest (S21), midway or 90° apart (S71) and farthest to each other (S13-1), respectively. From the figure, signal propagation improvement over the whole frequency band can be observed when using the MTS. A similar pattern is also observed for Phantom 2. Investigating the recorded frequency range while processing the measured data indicated a frequency range of 0.6-0.8 GHz as the optimum frequency band for image reconstruction when using the Huygens algorithm. An average gain of 4.8 dB when using the MTS is achieved in this frequency range.

Figs. 25(a) and (b) show the intensity images of Phantom 1 without the use of MTS obtained through Huygens algorithm, before and after image normalization and adjusting, respectively. Similarly, Figs. 26(a) and (b) represent the images of the same phantom when placing the MTS on the antennas. We can see a clear improvement of the images after the use of MTS where the target is detected and localized in its approximate position without noticeable artefacts. The actual location of the target is shown with a red circle.

Figs. 27(a) and (b) present the intensity images of Phantom 2 without the use of MTS obtained through Huygens algorithm, before and after image normalization and adjusting, respectively. The corresponding images of the same phantom after placing the MTS design are depicted in Figs. 28(a) and (b). Once again, the noticeable effect of using MTS can be observed by comparing the images.

It should be emphasized that as an input, Huygens algorithm only requires the electrical properties of the background medium where the antennas are placed (in this case 90% glycerol). Thus, we assigned the measured permittivity and conductivity values of 17 and 1.1 S/m respectively to the algorithm to perform the correct reconstructions in previous figures. In order to examine the robustness of the Huygens algorithms with respect to the uncertainty in the knowledge of the electrical properties of the background medium, we repeated the reconstruction of the data from Phantom 1 first assuming a permittivity of 27 (Fig. 29(a)), and then assuming a permittivity of 5 and conductivity of 0.5 S/m (Fig. 29(b)).

FIGURE 22. Reconstructed dielectric constant of Phantom 2 at different frequencies using experimental data and antennas with the MTS.

FIGURE 23. Reconstruction error metrics (at 1.2 GHz) for DBIM-TwIST simulations and measurements.

It can be observed that not having the exact knowledge of the background medium's electrical properties does not impact our detection capability, while it has a minor effect on the localization through creating an offset.

An interesting point to note is that Huygens algorithm's best reconstructions are produced using a lower frequency range of 0.6-0.8 GHz (likely due to greater penetration depth) while the DBIM-TwIST performs the best at higher frequencies between 1-1.5 GHz. This can be a great consideration for a hybrid imaging algorithm that can make use of both the lower and higher measured frequency bands for an optimum image reconstruction. A further point to address

FIGURE 24. S21 magnitude (dB) plots for different antenna distances within frequency band of 0.5-2 GHz for Phantom 1. Solid lines represent MTS measurement while dashed lines represent no MTS measurement.

FIGURE 25. Radar-based images for Phantom 1 using experimental data and antennas without the MTS : (a) Images before normalizing; (b) Images after normalization and thresholding adjustment. Axes units are meters.

FIGURE 26. Radar-based images for Phantom 1 using experimental data and antennas with the MTS : (a) Images before normalizing; (b) Images after normalization and thresholding adjustment. Axes units are meters.

FIGURE 27. Radar-based images for Phantom 2 using experimental data and antennas without the MTS : (a) Image before normalizing; (b) Image after normalization and thresholding adjustment. Axes units are meters.

would be the challenge of overcoming the “no target” reference scenario used here for image subtraction, which will be unavailable in real-life clinical scenarios. Our next simulations and measurements will assess this key challenge by increasing our algorithms' robustness when facing the absence of prior information.

FIGURE 28. Radar-based images for Phantom 2 using experimental data and antennas with the MTS : (a) Image before normalizing; (b) Image after normalization and thresholding adjustment. Axes units are meters.

FIGURE 29. Radar-based normalized and adjusted images for Phantom 1 using experimental data and antennas with the MTS, when assuming background electrical properties: (a) $\epsilon = 27$, $\sigma = 1.1$ S/m; (b) $\epsilon = 5$, $\sigma = 0.5$ S/m. Axes units are meters.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new design of a MTS which can be used on our custom-made triangular antennas, and permits a considerable performance enhancement resulting in improvements in both target detection and localization. In addition, we presented for the first time a MWI system that can use successfully both a radar-based and a tomographic algorithm on simulated and measured data collected from two brain phantoms and a purpose-built prototype. The presented simulation and measurement results verify that both algorithms can detect and localize the haemorrhagic stroke mimicking target in its approximate location, if the background signal in the absence of the target is known. In both our simulations and measurements, the target was placed on two different locations to assess the detectability of the algorithms. Our results indicate that the proposed MTS design improves target localization and decreases image artefacts for the tomographic algorithm and enables target's detection through our radar technique. The more profound effect of the MTS on the radar results is likely due to the iterative nature of the tomographic approach which reduces the possibility of error in detecting the correct target.

Future work will focus on several directions. We will work on optimizing the MTS design and testing it on our other in-house produced antennas. With respect to the phantom design, our next investigation will involve constructing more inhomogeneous and complex brain phantoms. This will permit us to more realistically mimic the head's complex internal structure and have a better understanding of the applicability extent of the algorithm for brain stroke detection. Building on the results presented here, we will proceed to develop a hybrid image processing algorithm,

which will combine the most prominent features of both the Huygens and DBIM-TwIST methods discussed in this paper. Our research will continue towards development of the system into a faster, more efficient and practical prototype for microwave imaging.

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